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The Global Environmental Performance Index

Between 2013 and 2022, it decreased by a value of -16.92%.

The Environmental Performance Index evaluates how countries manage and improve environmental resources, considering aspects such as air quality, water resource management, biodiversity protection, climate change policies, and waste management. This index reflects the balance between economic development and environmental sustainability, promoting sustainable innovation in the long term.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Environmental_Performance_Index

The Global Environmental Performance Index in 2022. Analyzing the 2022 data related to the Environmental Performance Index reveals significant differences between countries in terms of resource management and sustainability. Denmark emerges as the undisputed leader with a score of 77.9, closely followed by the United Kingdom with 77.7 and Finland with 76.5. These countries, known for their advanced environmental policies and focus on sustainability, represent virtuous examples of how innovation can be integrated with environmental protection. Other Nordic countries, such as Sweden (72.7) and Iceland (62.8), along with small states like Luxembourg (72.3) and Malta (75.2), also show high levels of environmental performance, highlighting how nations with limited resources can achieve excellent results through effective policies and targeted investments. The presence of Slovenia (67.3) and Austria (66.5) at the top of the ranking underscores Central Europe's constant commitment to sustainability. In contrast, large economies like the United States (51.1) and China (28.4) are in much lower positions, suggesting that economic size does not always translate into good environmental management. This could be attributed to various factors, including less stringent environmental policies, a high level of industrialization, and logistical challenges related to managing vast territories and large populations. Countries like Germany (62.4) and France (62.5) show moderate scores, indicating that despite technological advances and advanced environmental policies, there are still areas for improvement in resource management and environmental impact reduction. Other European countries like Estonia (61.4) and Latvia (61.1) are in a similar position, followed by Croatia (60.2) and Slovakia (60). Outside of Europe, Australia (60.1) and New Zealand (56.7) show a good balance between economic development and environmental sustainability. However, Japan (57.2) and South Korea (46.9) have lower scores, indicating that environmental challenges in these industrialized nations remain significant. The data analysis also shows that some emerging and developing countries, like Botswana (54), Namibia (50.9), and Costa Rica (46.3), are

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making notable progress, demonstrating that it is possible to advance environmental policies even with limited resources. In Latin America, Chile (46.7) and Ecuador (46.5) are among the best in the region, while Brazil (43.6) and Argentina (41.1) face more significant challenges. Many countries in the Middle East, like the United Arab Emirates (52.4), Qatar (33), and Saudi Arabia (37.9), have variable scores, reflecting different strategies and priorities in terms of environmental management. The presence of abundant energy resources often results in less incentive to invest in environmental sustainability. In the African continent, there is a wide range of performances. Countries like Kenya (30.8), Rwanda (32.8), and Senegal (33.9) show promising commitments to improving environmental policies. However, nations like Niger (37.7), Burkina Faso (35.5), and Mozambique (31.7) still face significant difficulties in improving their environmental performance. Finally, extremely low scores from countries like Vietnam (20.1), Myanmar (19.4), and India (18.9) reflect severe environmental issues that require urgent interventions and significant reforms. India, in particular, with its rapid economic growth and vast population, faces enormous challenges in terms of pollution, water resource management, and biodiversity. Overall, the 2022 Environmental Performance Index data shows a varied landscape, where the commitment and policies adopted by different countries play a crucial role in determining their position in the ranking. While some countries are successfully advancing towards greater sustainability, others still need to make significant efforts to improve their environmental management and ensure a greener and more sustainable future for future generations.

The Global Environmental Performance Index between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of data related to the Environmental Performance Index between 2013 and 2022 reveals significant trends in various countries, with some improving their environmental management considerably and others recording worrying declines. Malta, with an impressive increase of 26.70 points, rising from 48.5 to 75.2, represents the best example of improvement, demonstrating a percentage increase of 55.05%. This significant progress suggests that Malta has likely implemented more effective environmental policies and invested in green technologies, managing to greatly improve environmental quality. Kazakhstan saw an increase of 8.00 points, rising from 32.9 to 40.9, with a percentage increase of 24.32%. Although less impressive than Malta, this improvement still reflects a positive effort in resource management. Denmark, with an increase of 14.30 points from 63.6 to 77.9 and an improvement of 22.48%, continues to prove itself a leader in environmental sustainability, further strengthening its already high position thanks to innovative policies and strong ecological awareness. Finland improved its score by 12.10 points, rising from 64.4 to 76.5, an increase of 18.79%, continuing to consolidate its commitment to sustainability. Uzbekistan recorded an increase of 6.00 points, from 32.2 to 38.2, with a percentage improvement of 18.63%, signaling a progressive attention to environmental issues. Romania improved by 7.70 points, from 48.3 to 56, with an increase of 15.94%, closely followed by North Macedonia with an increase of 7.30 points, from 47 to 54.3, equivalent to 15.53%. On the contrary, many countries have seen a significant deterioration in their environmental performance. Vietnam recorded the worst decrease, dropping by 30.50 points from 50.6 to 20.1, with a percentage loss of 60.28%. This drastic decline reflects severe environmental problems, probably due to rapid industrial development not accompanied by adequate sustainability measures. Yemen also suffered an extreme decrease, dropping from 35.5 to 0, with a 100% loss, indicating a total collapse in environmental management, likely due to conflicts and political instability. Nepal lost 29.70 points, dropping from 58 to 28.3, with a percentage decrease of 51.21%, followed by the Philippines, which lost 28.50 points, dropping from 57.4 to 28.9, with a decrease of 49.65%. These countries probably face significant challenges such as deforestation, air and water pollution, and ineffective waste management. Indonesia also suffered a severe decline, losing 24.10 points from 52.3 to 28.2, with a decrease of 46.08%, reflecting problems like massive deforestation and industrial pollution. Malaysia saw a decline of 27.50 points, from 62.5 to 35, with a percentage

loss of 44%, suggesting that despite economic development, environmental sustainability has been neglected. Guatemala also recorded a significant loss of 23.90 points, dropping from 51.9 to 28, with a decrease of 46.05%, indicating serious environmental problems possibly related to urbanization and waste management. Countries like Nigeria registered a decrease of 11.80 points, dropping from 40.1 to 28.3, with a loss of 29.43%, reflecting persistent challenges in natural resource management and pollution mitigation. The situation is similar in countries like Argentina and Brazil, which saw declines of 15.40 and 17.30 points, with percentage decreases of 27.26% and 28.41%, respectively. These declines indicate problems such as Amazon deforestation and the lack of effective environmental policies. Even developed countries are not exempt from declines in environmental performance. The United States saw a decrease of 5.50 points, dropping from 56.6 to 51.1, with a loss of 9.72%, signaling a retreat in environmental policies perhaps due to administrative changes and variable political priorities. Japan recorded a decline of 6.20 points, dropping from 63.4 to 57.2, with a decrease of 9.78%, reflecting difficulties in adapting its environmental policies to its industrialized economy. In Europe, Germany saw a decline of 4.50 points, from 66.9 to 62.4, with a loss of 6.73%, indicating that even countries with advanced environmental policies can face complex challenges. France lost 6.50 points, dropping from 69 to 62.5, with a decrease of 9.42%, reflecting possible difficulties in implementing consistent green policies. Spain also saw a decrease of 3.70 points, dropping from 60.3 to 56.6, with a loss of 6.14%. Other European countries like Austria and Hungary recorded declines of 2.40 and 2.00 points, with losses of 3.48% and 3.50%, respectively, while Iceland saw a decline of 3.50 points, with a decrease of 5.28%. These data indicate that although Europe is generally at the forefront of environmental policies, there are still areas needing significant improvements.

Conclusions. The value of the Environmental Performance Index has decreased on average for the countries considered between 2013 and 2022 by a value of -16.92%, going from an amount of 54 units to a value of 44.8 units. Some countries have seen the level of the Environmental Performance Index grow significantly more than the average, namely Malta with a value of +55.05%, Kazakhstan with +24.32%, Denmark with +22.48%, Kuwait with +19.44%, Finland with +18.79%. There are also countries where the value of the Environmental Performance Index has decreased significantly between 2013 and 2022, such as India with -47.79%, the Philippines with -49.65%, Nepal with -51.21%, Vietnam with -60.28%, and Yemen with -100.00%. Looking at the values for 2022, we can see that almost all Western countries and those with a medium-high per capita income have an Environmental Performance Index value above 50.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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